

Secure processing of health data: EOSC and EHDS approaches and synergies

Main highlights of the online workshop held on 4 February 2025

Both European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and European Health Data Space (EHDS) are facing a challenge of federating services for health data, the majority of which is highly sensitive. Sensitive data processing requires dedicated Secure Processing Environments (SPEs), also known as Trusted Research Environments (TREs). But what are the approaches adopted by the two initiatives when it comes to SPEs and TREs? Is there a European shared understanding on how these environments should be built in a way that they are interoperable across organisations and countries?

The virtual workshop on 4th of February 2025, organised by the [EOSC-ENTRUST project](#), focused on investigating how EOSC and EHDS can support each other in achieving TRE/SPE interoperability as well as to find other commonalities and synergies e.g. in sensitive data processing of research (secondary use). Moreover, the workshop was also a good opportunity to understand the contribution that the EOSC-ENTRUST project can bring to the two initiatives.

Around 100 experts working with the SPEs and sensitive data in the context of EOSC and/or EHDS joined the workshop. Participants came from EOSC-ENTRUST and its sister projects [TITAN](#) and [SIESTA](#), and [TEHDAS2](#) as well as from more broadly the EOSC and EHDS initiatives.

Main takeaways

- Sensitive datasets are fragmented and described in different ways, according to different classifications; in addition, the governance structures of the data vary. Data access and interoperability of data are the major challenges faced by TRE providers.
- EHDS regulation is in its implementation phase, making it difficult to discuss the data access topic and interoperability from a governance perspective. However, the regulatory aspects are well defined and agreed by the countries, and they state a key role of the countries in the governance. The EOSC-A Health Data Task Force is also at an early stage, expecting to produce relevant assets in the medium-term in

the landscape of sensitive data processing. The EOSC-ENTRUST project is producing a blueprint on TRE interoperability by the end of 2027.

- The data access, security and interoperability topics are addressed by both EOSC and EHDS (e.g. on regulatory level) initiatives and the EOSC-ENTRUST project respectively, underlining the need to synchronise the efforts: the EOSC-ENTRUST project has published a first version of the [blueprint for interoperability](#), outlining the capabilities and requirements of TREs while the TEHDAS2 project, funded to support the implementation of EHDS regulation, is working with the technical specifications for SPEs. There are overlaps that should be transformed in synergies.
- Technologies evolve fast, making it important to re-examine the regulation regularly.
- Use of AI in TRE infrastructure is a complicated challenge, for example, guaranteeing the models do not contain sensitive data when transferred between TREs.
- Standardisation is a topic to be further examined – some existing practices are in place but have turned out to be challenging.
- The participants found the workshop very useful to address overlaps and ensure knowledge sharing and alignment – in future we need joint opportunities and solutions are needed to make the federation work for European users.

More detailed notes from the meeting can be found below:

Programme and materials

9:00 Welcome from session chair, Tim Hubbard, ELIXIR, the European life science infrastructure

9:10 Presentation: Gaps and commonalities in health data access, security and interoperability services, Juan González, EOSC-A Health Data Task Force / IACS

9:20 Presentation: Approaches to SPE/TRE in the European Health Data Space, Irini Kessissoglou, DG SANTE, European Commission

9:30 Presentation: Blueprint of EOSC-ENTRUST to enhance European interoperability, Pål Sætrom, EOSC-ENTRUST / Norwegian University of Science and Technology

9:45 Panel discussion and start of Q&A: How to ensure interoperability of European SPEs/TREs: challenges and synergies

Moderator: Ignacio Blanquer, EOSC-A

Panelists: Irini Kessissoglou (EC, DG SANTE), Pål Sætrum (EOSC-ENTRUST / Norwegian University of Science and Technology), Juan González (EOSC-A Health Data Task Force / IACS), Miikka Kallberg (SPE subgroup in Health Data Access Bodies – community of practice / CSC – IT Center for Science)

10:30 Workshop ends

Welcome and introductions to the topic

Tim Hubbard from ELIXIR kicked off the meeting by outlining the concept of TREs and introducing the initiatives and infrastructures for sensitive data, such as ELIXIR network, [1+ Million Genomes initiative](#), [FEGA](#) (co-developed by ELIXIR), and the [ELIXIR Beacon network](#). This presentation introduced EOSC-ENTRUST objectives in the context of the European data spaces.

Setting the scene – gaps and commonalities in health data access

Juan González (IACS), a co-chair of the [EOSC Association Health Data Task Force](#), and former coordinator of the [Healthy Cloud project](#), was invited to the workshop to contextualise the health data access topic, to give an overview of the landscape we are operating in and to showcase the role of EOSC in sensitive data for research. The presentation outlined the background for sensitive data access and processing topics through previous projects and initiatives, outlining the major services in the context and the regulation governing the use of sensitive data.

The presentation showed that there is heavy fragmentation, diverse governance structures, and multiple formats of health data. The key question is: how to access the different types and entries of data and how to ensure the interoperability?

The EOSC Health Data Task Force's answer to the health data challenge is to define EOSC's strategy towards the extensive use of health data in research projects by identifying requirements, regulations and ethical and legal grounds to make the access and processing of health data fair and safe in EOSC context, foster interoperability with EHDS for secondary use infrastructure, and to build networks and partnerships mobilising EOSC and EHDS communities. So far, the Task Force has identified stakeholders and tried to understand the alignment of both EOSC and EHDS. The aim is to propose exchange channels between the two initiatives and to provide solutions and resources from the EOSC ecosystem to the EHDS ecosystem and vice versa including TREs.

Policy approaches to SPEs/TREs in European Health Data Space (EHDS)

Irini Kessissoglou from the European Commission (Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety) introduced the audience to the European Health Data Space policy approach to secondary use of health data access and Secure Processing Environments.

The European Health Data Space is a regulation that governs the use of primary and secondary use of health data. The aim of the regulation in the context of secondary use is to make the data available for research and policy-making in a safe and secure way. The regulation outlines the request for access to health data through Health Data Access Bodies, who ensure the data holders upload permitted data in the right format, that SPEs are compliant and that data access is correctly controlled. SPEs will be audited and must develop tools and computing services to meet user requirements. The regulation also controls the longevity of data permits and the time the data can be within the SPE as well as the security measures (organisational and technical specifications) of the compliant SPEs.

The following figure shows the TRE/SPE placement in the Data User Journey:

[HealthData@EU Pilot is a project](#), designing, developing, deploying and operating a network of nodes federated by central services to create a pilot infrastructure (the HealthData@EU infrastructure) for reusing health data and scaling towards EU-wide infrastructure. It connects data platforms and develops services supporting the user journey for research projects demonstrated above.

This cross-border secondary use infrastructure will receive central support services provided by the European Commission, deploy national Health Data Access Bodies and National Registries, and include data access services, such as Secure Processing

Environments (SPEs) for Secondary Use. The European Commission Secure Processing Environment will analyse pseudonymised health data coming from Union institutions, bodies offices or agencies.

TEHDAS2 develops the technical specifications, feeding in to the implementing act of EHDS and the guideline for users of SPEs.

EOSC ENTRUST blueprint in addressing the interoperability challenge

Pål Sætrom (NTNU), a partner in the EOSC-ENTRUST project, presented the first year version of the Blueprint EOSC-ENTRUST. The focus of the first version of the Blueprint is on interoperability, which the document addresses through requirements from research domains and capabilities from existing TREs. The document addresses the question “what is needed to form a federation of TRE providers?”. Rather than specifying the minimum TRE requirements such as Specific SATRE levels or ISO27001, the recommendation is that a federation should agree on some minimum standard.

The next steps forward with the Blueprint is to gather internal input through gap analyses, refined user journeys and requirements. In addition, the project will monitor external developments to refine the Blueprint. The Blueprint for the second year of the project will outline the operating procedures and interface definitions.

Discussion: How to ensure interoperability of European SPEs/TREs: challenges and synergies

The last section of the programme was a panel discussion and Q&A, during which the presenters joined the discussion – a new panellist was also introduced (Miikka Kallberg, CSC – IT center for Science, SPE subgroup in Health Data Access Bodies – community of practice and ENTRUST project). The discussion centred around datasets, access to them within the European Health Data Space regulation, location of data within SPEs and the federation of health data. The role of EC’s SPE subgroup was also introduced briefly.

- The current aim of the EC’s SPE subgroup in Health Data access bodies is to discuss what is the “security” in “Secure Processing Environment”
- There is no agreement on the definition of dataset – one example is to define thematic datasets to cover different topics. Also, datasets should be linked to each other.
- Technological specifications in the implementing acts of EHDS – technical specifications created by TEHDAS2 project look into the technologies of today but the implementing acts can be amended as technologies change. The main issue is

the security and technical requirements. The SPE subgroup is discussing what is the right level of specifications that is needed.

- Data use and governing of requirements, and access to data - the roles for governing SPEs in EHDS has been mapped by the EOSC-ENTRUST project and addressing this is on the future agenda. This is a topic the regulation addresses but as long as SPE complies with technical specifications, a health data access body can decide to put data in that environment. Furthermore, there should be a market for SPEs. In some countries, such as Finland, there are different SPEs that are audited against regulation of national legislators and you can decide the SPE you use for research.
- AI should not be released to secure environment as machine learning is not safe in the environments – one solution is to train the model and use the interface but the model needs to stay where it is
 - It is difficult to train models and make sure there is no personal data in the model – TEHDAS2 technical specifications will evaluate if there is a tool to detect personal data in the model. Another option is to have secure processing environments that are compliant with each other and can transfer AI models from one to another but the AI stays in one environment.
 - It is important to address this issue soon to facilitate organised AI model
- In many cross-border use cases there are types of analysis of sensitive data where you need to move the data but GDPR gives restrictions. In some cases you need to move data and workflows but the quality is not consistent in the workflows – it is therefore necessary to take data from one place and put into another in some cases and sometimes legislation restricts this, often national.
 - A federated approach is the answer here but you need to also build public trust
 - The barriers for moving data are often social and political rather than technical and legal – federated system can cover the heavy data transfers
- Standards and security in federated analysis – there are safe practices but the main challenge is ensuring the communication between different nodes are secured. Once you export data the results should pass statistical control but there are no standards to it yet
- Federated search and wider set of clinical data – taking the next steps require standards, currently fragmentation and the effort of obliging data holders.
- Roles in EHDS and going forward
 - There are opportunities for joint solutions – EHDS represents a specific challenge and it is important to see how these can be generalised in other domains. These meetings are good for this purpose
 - The EOSC-A Health Data Task Force wants to find more opportunities to extend and put together both ecosystems to maximise the investments made. It also wants to also serve research communities

- Complementarities and synergies are needed as there is lots of expertise to be put together to create optimal specifications – collaboration e.g. between the SPE sub-group and TEHDAS2 is important here.
- All this activity here is the future way of dealing with sensitive data – infrastructures are available but lots of work is needed to make the federation to work for EC users